

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

Samsul Alam¹

Sr. Lecturer (MIS)

Department of Business Administration

Daffodil International University

Email: salam.bba@diu.edu.bd

Abstract

This study aims at finding factors of knowledge management (KM) that affect organizational performance (OP). Thus, the study will suggest possible research agenda in the field of knowledge management. To find out the factors, a systematic literature review method is adopted. The result finds some research area in KM effect on all organizational performance indicators (E.g. cost/price, quality, delivery, responsiveness and flexibility, Business metrics, Total cost of ownership), complete KM impact on financial analysis of the organization that represents the OP (e.g. Ratio Analysis) appropriately; prepare a questionnaire and perform a survey to represent the relationship between KM and OP; perform hypothesis testing, factor analysis, correlation, and regression analysis and prepare graphs using SPSS Software for the best representation of the results; draw a reliable conclusion and summary that will guide the organizations towards the importance of knowledge management.

Keywords factors identification, gap analysis, knowledge management, organizational performance, systematic literature review

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1. Introduction

Knowledge management is not a new concept, in fact it is more the result of old civilization. Till recent innovations, the old organized businesses have been looking for a competitive advantage because it allows them to serve customers as efficiently as possible, increase the profits, and have a set of loyal customers and can stay more in the competitive scene. KM is aimed at establishing a knowledge connection between employees in one organization, teaching the methods of organizational knowledge, providing the areas for changing individual knowledge to collective knowledge and vice versa in order to reinforce the innovation and creativity (Abbasi & Najafi, 2014). KM has various approaches and definitions according to the perspective and discipline of the individual or organization that engages with the concept. These include management, individual and organizational learning, communications, information systems and technology, artificial intelligence, intellectual assets that focus on the explicit capture and registration of knowledge (Lehaney, 2004). Knowledge is a limitless resource in the knowledge-based economy, therefore, organizations should learn, store, transfer and apply knowledge to add value or gain competitive advantage (Sveiby, 1997). KM refers to identifying and leveraging the collective knowledge within the organization to help in competing (von Krogh, 1998). But in a severe and dynamic environment, organizations should respond quickly to their rivals and their environment by transforming into a learning organization, an organic and flexible company, to foster knowledge flow and sharing among the departments and task groups (Lu & Tsai, 2004). KM is a relatively new term that encompasses not only the related notions of knowledge transfer and knowledge sharing (externally from other firms to the small firm and/or internally among firm members), but also the knowledge utilization process. There is relatively little empirical evidence though regarding the actual consequences of KM at the level of the individual firm, especially quantitative studies based on large random samples of small and medium-sized firms or SMEs (Uhlener et al., 2007). KM is the planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling of people, processes and systems in the organization to ensure that its knowledge-related assets are improved and effectively employed. Knowledge-related assets include knowledge in the form of printed documents

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

such as patents and manuals, knowledge stored in electronic repositories such as a “best-practices” database, employees’ knowledge about the best way to do their jobs, knowledge that is held by teams who have been working on focused problems and knowledge that is embedded in the organization’s products, processes and relationships (King, 2009). KM is about supporting innovation, the generation of new ideas. and the exploitation of the organization’s thinking power; capturing insight and experience to make them available and usable when, where, and by whom required; making it easy to find and re-use sources of know-how and expertise, whether they are recorded in physical form or held in someone’s mind; fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, continual learning and improvement; improving the quality of decision-making and other intelligent tasks; understanding the value and contribution of intellectual assets and increasing their worth, effectiveness, and exploitation (KPMG, 1999). Knowledge is not only a main resource for a company, but also a vital source of competitive gain. Therefore, entrepreneurs who are masters in information and knowledge stand to gain more benefits from the market. KM, branching from knowledge, is about the knowledge exploitation and improvement of a company to achieve the organization’s objectives. Moreover, KM attempts to solve the problematic paradoxes in business (Jenatabadi et al., 2013). Key assets for a company’s competitiveness were physical assets and financial capital. These assets still represent and will continue to represent important factors for competitiveness. However, more recently, due to the complexity and turbulence of the competitive scenario, companies have recognized the need for increasing the level of „intelligence“ embedded in their processes and products and then the importance of continuously improving their core competencies and knowledge. Therefore, looking for new differentiators and drivers of bottom line performance, companies have recognized the relevance of knowledge assets as key sources of competitive advantage (Schiuma & Carlucci, 2004).

KM is largely an organizational activity that focuses on what managers can do to enable KM’s goals to be achieved, how they can motivate individuals to participate in achieving them and how they can create social processes that will facilitate KM success. Social processes include communities of practice – self-organizing groups of people who share a common interest – and expert networks –

networks that are established to allow those with less expertise to contact those with greater expertise. Such social processes are necessary because while knowledge initially exists in the mind of an individual, for KM to be successful, knowledge must usually be transmitted through social groups, teams and networks (Farsan et al., 2013). KM serves to create value from an organization's intangible assets. Many organizations have adopted KM practices in recent years. Some of those organizations have achieved success at KM, but others have not (Gupta, 2004). Knowledge creation is in fact just one of many activities involved in KM. Others include identifying, acquiring, sharing, retaining, refining, and using knowledge. (Heisig 2009) compared 160 different KM frameworks: no fewer than 117 of them included a list of activities. Global interest in KM, both academic and practical, has continued to increase throughout the last two decades, but as these numbers indicate, consensus on the theory underpinning KM remains some way off (Edwards, 2015). Knowledge is increasingly being recognized as the new strategic imperative of organizations. The most established paradigm is that knowledge is power. Both tacit and explicit knowledge enable organizations to respond to novel situations and emerging challenges. Tacit knowledge is personal. It is stored in the heads of people. It is accumulated through study and experience. It is developed through the process of interaction with other people. Tacit knowledge grows through the practice of trial and error and the experience of success and failure. Explicit knowledge is codified. It is stored in documents, databases, websites, emails and the like. It is knowledge that can be readily made available to others and transmitted or shared in the form of systematic and formal languages (Uriarte, 2008). Knowledge and KM are concepts which are debated extensively by managers, analyst and academicians. Managers ask for more information to support decisions. This led to the use of IT (Information Technology) to build transaction support system, management information systems and data warehouses resulting in too much information, which has neither helped the managers nor provided any value to the organizations. Data leads to information, but what organizations were really looking for was knowledge (Bhattacharya & Chaudhury, 2004). KM processes are significant predictors for organizational creativity, i.e., business organizations can achieve strategic and economic benefits of KM by utilizing organizational creativity in an effective fashion. Organizational structure and culture

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

are found to be significant in predicting the KM processes. In addition, it is noted that technology-related variables are not significantly related to the KM (Lee & Choi, 2000). Based on the notion that knowledge is the key organizational asset, researchers have argued that KM leads to positive OP. However, the impact has not been carefully demonstrated. Numerous organizations have experimented with KM to improve their performance but have not fully. Researchers have written about “knowledge management as a double edged sword”, the “deadliest sins of knowledge management”, the “vicious circle” of KM and “knowledge traps”. There is a challenge in the field to demonstrate how to manage organizational knowledge for performance (Singh et al., 2006). With effective and efficient KM process, most companies claims it will be helpful to OP. Accordingly, KM is taken for granted an important antecedent of organization performance or innovation (Darroch, 2005). But there are still some different results in KM sub-processes, or sub-dimensions, and OP. It needs to verify very carefully (Liao, S. 2009). Organizations that better apply the process of knowledge creation can connect knowledge in new ways, and present more value to customers by improving market offerings. According to Yong, et al (2009) when firms are better at knowledge creation through SECI process; they are more successful in reaching competence, development, and return. Thus generating new knowledge is vital since it has positive effect on performance (Abadi et al., 2013). It is very important for SMEs to know what their knowledge assets are, and how to manage and make best use of these assets to get maximum return, since without proper KM approaches; SMEs are likely to have more to lose than larger enterprises (Anand & Singh, 2011). KM increases the ability to learn from its environment and to incorporate knowledge into the business processes by adapting to new tools and technologies. While it is generally understood that a robust technological infrastructure plays a crucial role in helping educational institutions gather and analyze data to improve outcomes, the barriers to successful technology and information systems implementation in educational institutions can be attributed to a narrow understanding of just how these systems and technologies manifest themselves within organizations (Ranjan & Khalil, 2015).

Firms with adequate CKM (Customer Knowledge Management) policies will more likely detect emerging market opportunities than their competitors will. A medium level of CKM in the sample (average of 3.3 in a scale from 1 to 5) highlights the need to implement effective CKM in companies (for example, market research activities). Results emphasize collaborating with customers within the innovation process. Results also reveal the importance of a culture open to innovation. Customer collaboration and openness to innovation are key inputs to CKM because they affect CKM and marketing results. Working with these key inputs companies may improve CKM and consequently their performance, maintaining their competitive advantage (Fidel, P., et al., 2015). Knowledge-based view (KBV) suggests that knowledge plays a pivotal role in increasing the firms' competitive advantage and financial performance (Grant 1996; Takeuchi 2013; Zack et al. 2009). Nowadays organization must be able to gain required knowledge for product innovation and process improvement, and also disseminate knowledge among employees and implement it in daily life. That's the only way through which the organizations can fulfill the requirements of competitive environment and highly variable needs of customers (Aminy, 2006). The metaphor of transferring knowledge from hands into brain and changing information into knowledge and finally, into works or a determined output with added value means that variety, creativity, technology and knowledge-oriented of organization is an inevitable choice for the organizations in 21st century (Mehrara, A.et al., 2012). In the age of service and knowledge economy, firms have realized that obtaining, managing, and sharing customer knowledge can be a valuable resource to have advantages over their competitors (Pandey et al., 2015). We now know that the source of wealth is something specifically human: knowledge. If we apply knowledge to tasks we already know how to do, we call it productivity. If we apply knowledge to tasks that are new and different, we call it innovation. Only knowledge allows us to achieve those two goals (Drucker, 2002). Organizations and structural equations modeling help academics and managers in designing KM strategic schedules in order to obtain higher effectiveness, efficiency and profit capacity (Maroofi, 2015). Coupled with the rapid rise of hybrid networks, the challenge for many surviving network providers is to maintain profit margins through efficient asset management of their physical products while migrating to a more services-oriented business model,

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

where additional revenues derive from enhanced network solutions, integration services capabilities, and telecommunications consultancy. This places greater emphasis on the importance of managing knowledge to support and secure such a change in strategic intent (Taylor & Schellenberg, 2005). Knowledge-based society sustained by knowledge-based economy signifies a new era for education; information and the correlation of economic data in complex contexts. In this framework, knowledge becomes increasingly important for economic power and social cohesion, as well as for the increase in people's living standards. The social transformations cause a new perspective over education with information gaps and social isolation (Yaghoubi, et al., 2011). Establishing clear work responsibilities for all employees, an element of organizational trust, was found to be a significant element that contributes significantly to OP (Paliszkievicz & Koohang, 2013). Most organizations have a high KMI. However, the organizations expect more from their KM practices and CSF than these practices and success factors can actually offer. Furthermore, we noted that the KMI is positively related to OP and could serve as a predictor of OP (Asoh, Crnkovic, & Belardo, 2004). Each company has trading Relationships with customers, suppliers and many others in their work environment and how structured thesis relationships will have a significant impact on the ease with all which knowledge flows inside and outside the firm. Also, firms use more external knowledge sources as significant to improve performance and to generate a competitive advantage (Maâlej, Rim, & Affes, 2014). Organizations put their focus on organizational knowledge rather than on material resources. They increase their efforts to maximize knowledge utilization in order to cope with global trends, improve their business processes, make effective decisions, improve the quality of their products/services, and increase their effectiveness. The successful management of organizational knowledge leads organizations one step further in their work, and it is an important factor in gaining and maintaining a competitive advantage. The KM processes can be facilitated and supported by various information technologies and techniques. Some of the information techniques and technologies give better effects in KM processes than others (Blazeska-Tabakovska & Manevska, 2015). Effective knowledge activities in healthcare not only improve the existing operational capabilities of healthcare service but also reduce the care delivery costs and prevent potential medical errors (Agarwal et al. 2010; Wang et

al. 2013). If the organization can nurture an adhocracy culture, it will be easy to create an environment where knowledge workers can learn, feel comfortable, and have the opportunity to be creative and innovative, improve corporate performance and increase the organization's value (Tseng, 2010).

The relationship between the level of knowledge and OP has been studied by the academic community and is receiving growing attention from decision makers in organizations. Not so with the feedback relationship between performance and the level of knowledge, although this relationship has a dynamic pattern of behavior of both variables (Arenas, 2002). Although knowledge has for a long time been recognized as a key resource for achieving and sustaining competitive advantage, only in recent years the need to efficiently and effectively manage it has emerged clearly, especially as a consequence of the increased possibilities offered by the Internet-related information and communication technologies (ICTs). Actually, such technologies have dramatically reduced costs and increased speed, spatial reach, and amount of information and knowledge flows (Becerra-Fernandez & Sabherwal, 2005; Kim & Trimi, 2007). New technologies and tools have emerged in recent years that are of great importance for KM, organizational learning, and knowledge-building purposes. They provide communication facilities with new-style opportunities for organizational learning and collaborative knowledge building, because they facilitate and support a specific form of interplay between individual and social knowledge processes (Kimmerle et al. 2010). There has been little research that decomposes the effects of KM in relation to OP. The results suggest the decomposed approach is useful for understanding the complex relationships embodied in the KM-performance link, which cannot be surmised from a composite model. Such an approach is useful for research aimed at acquiring an in-depth understanding of KM, as opposed to achieving parsimony or focusing on main effects (Fattahiyan et al., 2012). It is obvious that knowledge is slowly becoming the most important factor of production, next to labor, land and capital. Even though some forms of intellectual capital are transferable, internal knowledge is not easily copied. This means that the knowledge anchored in employees' minds can get lost if they decide to leave the organization. Therefore, the key objective of

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

management is to improve the processes of acquisition, integration and usage of knowledge, which is exactly what KM is all about (Rašul et al., 2012). Understanding of what constitutes knowledge is central to its effective management (Pathirage et al., 2007).

2. Gap Analysis

Recommendations of areas where research is needed:

- Research unavailability considering Bangladesh perspective
- Research unavailability considering all OP indicators (E.g. cost/price, quality, delivery, responsiveness and flexibility, Business metrics, Total cost of ownership)
- Research unavailability regarding complete KM impact on financial analysis of the organization that represents the OP(e.g. Ratio Analysis) appropriately
- Need to prepare a questionnaire and perform a survey to represent the relationship between KM and OP
- Need to perform hypothesis testing, factor analysis, correlation and regression analysis and prepare graphs using SPSS Software for the best representation of the results
- Need to draw a reliable conclusion and summary that will guide the organizations towards the importance of KM

3. Systematic Literature Review

SN	Year	Study Area	Variables	Methodology	Result
1.	2015	Effects on customer knowledge management and performance	Customer knowledge management, Innovation orientation, customer collaboration, marketing results, innovation process	Survey to 210 companies, Partial least square (PLS) technique, a variance-based structural equation modeling (SEM) Method.	Outcomes emphasize the relationships between customer collaboration, CKM, and marketing results. Results show that customer collaboration directly affects marketing results (H3: $\beta=0.098$; pb 0.05), with a less intense relation than that CKM has with marketing results (H4: $\beta = 0.405$; p b 0.001). Data analysis also demonstrates that, through CKM, customer collaboration indirectly affects marketing results. Finally, results indicate that customer collaboration is a more influential antecedent of CKM (H2: $\beta=0.349$; pb 0.001) than innovation orientation is (H1: $\beta=0.101$; p b 0.05).

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2.	2015	Business processes and Knowledge management	Tacit and explicit knowledge	Qualitative	Interest in managing knowledge has grown in step with the perception that increasingly we live in a knowledge-based economy.
3.	2015	Strategic knowledge management, innovation, and performance	Tacit (codification) & Explicit (personalization)	Qualitative	Based on an empirical study consisted of 195 Iranian organizations and structural equations modeling which help academics and managers in designing KM strategic schedules in order to obtain higher effectiveness, efficiency and profit capacity.
4.	2015	The Impact of knowledge management information system on businesses	Multimedia design of knowledge management system	Qualitative	The Knowledge Management Information Systems (KMIS) are established is the knowledge. Compared to data which presents a collection of unprocessed and unanalyzed facts, records, events and information that signifies organized and processed data which are temporarily correct, the knowledge has strong experience and reflexive elements which differentiate it from the information in a certain context.
5.	2007	Application of knowledge management in Management education: A conceptual framework	knowledge management, business schools, education, faculty, students, courses	Qualitative	The real success of KM in B-schools lies in helping the students grow into worthy human beings with courage to face the problems with an inner strength.
6.	2014	Relationship between the use of KM and employee performance in an organization of General Governor office of Zanjan	Knowledge; management; employee performance	Descriptive studies, SPSS 18	Knowledge Creation is 3.3 with the standard deviation of 0.86, moreover the minimum and maximum amounts for Knowledge Creation are 1 and 4.7 respectively.
7.	2014	The relationship between the sources of KM	External and internal sources of	Sampling of empirical research, exploratory	There is a relationship between internal sources of knowledge and OP, with a correlation coefficient ($CR= 6.055 > 1.96$)

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

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		and OP	knowledge and OP	analysis (SPSS 18) and the confirmatory analysis (AMOS structural equation method)	and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$.
8.	2013	Organizational trust as a foundation for knowledge sharing and its influence on OP	KM, trust, organizational trust, OP, knowledge sharing, innovation	Measures of organizational trust questionnaire and measure of OP questionnaire	Regression analyses revealed a valid model and that the relationship between OP and the OT isn't linear. It was found that OT8 - establishing clear work responsibilities is a significant item contributing to OP.
9.	2013	Relationship between KM and organizational learning among physical education teachers	KM, organizational learning, physical education teachers, organization	Survey questionnaire and hypothesis testing	The correlation between KM and overall organizational learning was that significant at the level of $P < 0.05$.
10.	2013	Explore linkage between KM and OP in Asian food manufacturing industry	KM, Organizational learning, OP	Survey questionnaire and path analysis	1) Linkage between KM and OP (OP): KM is positively related to OP, meaning more KM show higher capability in enhancing OP in the food manufacturing industry. (2) Linkage between KM and OL: KM is positively related to OL, meaning more KM show higher capability in enhancing OL in the food manufacturing industry. (3) Linkage between OL and OP: OL is positively related to OP, meaning more OL show higher capability in enhancing OP in the food manufacturing industry.
11.	2013	Relationship between Knowledge Creation Process and OP in a Service-Sector Organization	Tacit and explicit knowledge, OP	Survey questionnaire and hypothesis testing	A positive important bond was found between knowledge creation and OP (Beta=0.828, C.R = 6.468).
12.	2012	Relationship between KM	KM enablers, KM	Correlational descriptive	Consistent with expectations, the study results provided strong empirical support

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		enablers and processes with OP	processes, OP, university.	research and two kinds of survey questionnaires	for the decomposed model, accounting for 0.754 of the variance observed for OP.
13.	2012	The impact of knowledge Management on organizational performance	KM maturity, information technology, OP, structural equation modeling, survey research	Empirical research, Seven-point Likert scale	The Root mean square Residual index (RMR) is based on the residual matrix and is used to compare the fit of two different models with the same data. Values of the standardized RMR index lower 0.05 represent a good model fit.
14.	2011	Relationship between tactical processes of knowledge management and organizational intelligence in Iran	Organizational intelligence, KM, tactical processes, public sector	Quantitative (hypothesis testing & survey)	0.71% variation in OI is determined by tactical processes of KM. There is thus a meaningful relation between the criterion and predictor variable.
15.	2010	Interplay between individual and collective knowledge	KM, knowledge building, Organizational learning	Qualitative	KM is positively related to Organizational learning, meaning more KM show higher capability in enhancing OL in the organization.
16.	2009	Correlation between organizational culture and knowledge conversion on corporate performance	1. clan culture 2. adhocracy culture 3. market culture 4. hierarchy culture 5. Socialization 6. externalization 7. combination 8. internalization	Questionnaire and statistical analytical techniques were applied to gain best exploration on organizational culture, knowledge conversion and corporate performance.	An adhocracy culture enables knowledge conversion and enhances corporate performance more than clan and hierarchy cultures.
17.	2009	Relationship	KM, OP,	Hypothesis testing,	The path between OL and partnership

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

SN	Year	Study Area	Variables	Methodology	Result
		among KM, organizational learning, and OP	organizational learning, structural equation modeling	Likert scale	performance is significant positive (Beta=0.35, t-value=2.66). But the path between OL and financial performance and marketing performance are non-significant positive (Beta=0.16, t-value=1.30; Beta=0.17, T-value=1.36). Therefore, the findings partially support the relationship between the firm's OL and its OP (H3).
18.	2009	KM and organizational learning	Tacit and explicit knowledge, KM processes, organizational processes	Qualitative	KM focuses on knowledge processes – knowledge creation, acquisition, refinement, storage, transfer, sharing and utilization. These processes support organizational processes involving innovation, individual learning, collective learning and collaborative decision making.
19.	2007	Relationship between KM, innovation and firm performance of Dutch SMEs	KM, growth of small firms, entrepreneurship, innovation, micro data	Survey questionnaire and hypothesis testing	KM and/or innovation variables are (simultaneously) included for which at least one size-class coefficient is significant at the 5% level.
20.	2006	KM Capability and OP	Knowledge, management, OP	Qualitative	Larger organizations have a greater need to manage their knowledge.
21.	2005	Measuring organizational readiness for knowledge management	Instrument to evaluate the knowledge-sharing culture and information infrastructure	Qualitative and quantitative data from a survey of five European sites	More significantly, the need for senior managers to be in agreement about the strategic direction of their business and the strategic alignment between business strategy and knowledge-management strategy. Without such consensus, KM is likely to remain, at best, a series of fragmented and unrelated initiatives at local levels.
22.	2004	KM and its utilization	KM Initiatives, knowledge sharing, knowledge based assets	Qualitative	KM for corporate is mainly for getting competitive advantages over the rival companies. In developed countries this culture is running for quite some time where as in developing countries especially in India it is slowly picking up.
23.	2004	Relationship	KMI Model &	Quantitative (18	(1) To a significant degree, organizations

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		between the KM Index and OP	OP	managers from 6 European organizations were surveyed)	expect more from their KM efforts than these initiatives have delivered (2) KM realization in government is not significantly different from those in private organizations, and (3) the KMI is positively related to OP. Two important management implications emerge from this study: (1) the KMI is a simple and useful index that can be used to characterize KM, especially when organizations cannot afford expensive benchmarking or other assessment metrics and (2) it can serve as a proxy for and predictor of OP.
24.	2004	Investigation to an enabling role of km between learning organization and organizational learning	Knowledge, management, organizational learning and performance	Qualitative	An enabling role of KM could change the interaction between the learning organization and organizational learning.
25.	2004	Knowledge-based foundations of op improvements	Knowledge assets, new product development, performance improvement, knowledge assets management; action research	Action research	The implementation of the KM initiatives have proved to generate value for the company mainly in terms of both the reduction of the time to develop a new model of sofa, in particular the average time has been today reduced of 30%, and the improvement of the stylistic/functional conformity of the prototype to the product design, which guarantees a better alignment with customers" requirements.
26.	2002	The dynamics of the relationship between knowledge and OP	Sources of knowledge and OP	Simulation model	KM impacts the OP.
27.	2000	KM Enablers, Processes, and OP	KM Enablers, KM processes,	Socialization, externalization, combination, and	Organizational creativity was the significant predictors for nonfinancial performance of organization. That is, an

A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

SN	Year	Study Area	Variables	Methodology	Result
			KM intermediate outcome, OP	internalization	organization can achieve strategic benefits of KM from effective creation processes.

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A Systematic Literature Review to find out the Research Gap by identifying Factors affecting Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance

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